

Acceptor segregation and its impact on microstructure and conductivity in CaTiO_3

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1 Abstract

This study investigates the grain growth kinetics of CaTiO_3 and the impact of various transition metal dopants. Utilizing a combination of scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) accompanied by phase field simulations, we examine how the specific dopant species affects grain growth kinetics, segregation behavior, and defect chemistry. The dopants strongly influenced both grain growth and conductivities, showing that segregation and charge compensation does not occur similarly. This is likely driven by the energetic positions of the charge transition levels. The positions relative to the Fermi level dictate the distinct valence states within the host lattice, triggering varying degrees of ionic compensation and impacting segregation and grain boundary mobility via solute drag.

2 Introduction

Perovskite oxides (ABO_3) represent a vast and versatile class of functional ceramics with a variety of functional properties, including magnetic, electrical, optical and catalytical properties.[1] This is due to their flexible crystal structure that allows a wide range of substitution on both A- and B-site. The ideal perovskite structure is cubic and defined by a geometrical factor, the Goldschmidt factor of 1.[2] Compared to the extensively studied compounds SrTiO_3 (STO) and BaTiO_3 (BTO), the Goldschmidt factor of CaTiO_3 (CTO) is smaller than 1 and the structure shows an orthorhombic distortion (Pnma/Pbnm).[3]

Doping, i.e. the substitution of lattice atoms by heterovalent (transition metal) ions, is a common way to tailor a material's properties. Especially electronic properties can be tuned by introducing defect states into the band gap of a semiconducting perovskite oxide. This gives rise to a wide range of possible applications, including electrochemical, optical and catalytical devices.[4–6] Heterovalent substitution of lattice ions will increase the point defect concentration in a material, not only by the dopant species itself but also by different compensation mechanisms to maintain charge neutrality.[7] Point defects (e.g. oxygen vacancies, cation vacancies) play a crucial role in microstructure evolution of polycrystal materials. Various publications in literature report on the segregation and depletion of

different point defects in the grain boundary region of BaTiO₃, SrTiO₃ and other perovskite oxides caused by a positive core charge of the grain boundary.[8–13] These segregated species form a space charge layer (SCL) and can interact with grain boundaries and influence their mobility by causing solute drag.

The solute drag effect was originally observed for metals and describes the influence of solutes on the grain growth.[14] Furthermore, in ceramic materials a decrease in grain boundary migration is evident when impurities, e.g. dopants are present.[9,15] Different mobilities are consequence of the segregation of species (point defects) to the grain boundary. In (acceptor-doped) perovskite ceramics, positively charged oxygen vacancies segregate to the grain boundary core. Hence, grain boundaries exhibit a positive core charge, which causes negative defect species, such as acceptors, to segregate towards the interface.[7,12,13,16,17] Due to their slow diffusion, segregated defects cause a dragging force impeding grain boundary movement. The extend of dragging force depends on the defect concentration as depicted in **figure 1**: Higher defect concentrations increase the drag force on grain boundaries, impeding grain boundary migration and grain growth. As depicted in curve “III” in **figure 1**, a grain boundary can overcome its dragged state by exceeding a critical driving force. This can lead to different grain boundary types being present in the same system at the same time, dragged grain boundaries, with low velocity and non-dragged grain boundaries with high velocity. The presence of two grain boundary types with different mobilities can then result in bimodal microstructures with abnormal grain growth.[9,14,18]

Figure 1: Solute drag effect depending on doping concentration: $c(I)=0$, $c(II)<c(III)$. Illustrated by the author, adapted from Cahn.[14] Higher concentration leads to stronger deviation from the linear dependence of grain boundary velocity and driving force. Note the strong increase of velocity with a simultaneous decrease in required driving force in curve III. The dotted line represents the transition of the dragged to the non-dragged state of the grain boundary. The dependence on defect concentration becomes neglectable for non-dragged grain boundaries at high velocities.

The scope of this work is the quantification of grain growth in CaTiO_3 and the investigation of possible grain boundary transitions and bimodal microstructures due to solute drag as reported on for closely related materials like STO and BTO.[17,18] A prominent acceptor dopant in well investigated titanates like STO is iron, due to its similarity in ionic radius to Ti^{4+} and its preferred oxidation state of 3+.[9,19] The influence of different 3d-transition metal dopants besides Iron is investigated. The chosen dopants are Chromium, Manganese, Iron, and Cobalt. The microstructure evolution is observed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Phase field simulations give insights about segregation, defect concentration distributions and grain boundary core charge potentials. Segregation behavior and conductivities are investigated by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and are proven to be closely linked to the Fermi level and charge transition levels, giving an idea of how Fermi level engineering can be used to tailor grain boundary properties.

3 Experimental procedure

3.1 Powder preparation

All powders investigated in this work were prepared via solid-state synthesis using an attrition mill. For this purpose, the respective educts were combined and milled in 2-propanol for 4 hours at 1000 rpm using Y-TZP (Yttrium-stabilized Zirconia) balls (TOSOH, Japan) of 2 mm diameter. In the case of CTO, the educt powders CaCO_3 (Merck, Germany) and TiO_2 (Merck, Germany) were milled in a stoichiometric A/B-ratio of 0.995 ($\text{Ca}_{0.995}\text{Ti}_{1.00}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$) to avoid Calcium-rich secondary phases. For the acceptor doped-powders a ratio of 0.995/0.99/0.01 was used of CaCO_3 , TiO_2 and the respective dopant metal oxide ($\text{Ca}_{0.995}\text{Ti}_{0.99}\text{M}_{0.01}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ – M representing the respective metal atom). After removing the milling balls, the slurries were left to dry for 24 h at 70 °C. The dried powders were then sieved and calcined at 915 °C for 4 h. Five different powders were prepared: CaTiO_3 , $\text{CaTi}_{0.991}\text{Cr}_{0.001}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$, $\text{CaTi}_{0.99}\text{Mn}_{0.01}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$, $\text{CaTi}_{0.99}\text{Fe}_{0.01}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ and $\text{CaTi}_{0.99}\text{Co}_{0.01}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (denominated below as CTO, Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO, Fe:CTO and Co:CTO, respectively). The exact weight ratios used for the synthesis are given in **Table 1**.

Table 1: weight ratio of different educt powders for solid state synthesis of CaTiO₃ and acceptor-doped CaTiO₃

	CaCO ₃	TiO ₂	Cr ₂ O ₃ / Mn ₂ O ₃ / Fe ₃ O ₄ / Co ₃ O ₄
CTO	55.49 wt-%	44.51 wt- %	
Cr:CTO	55.52 wt-%	44.08 wt-%	0.41 wt-%
Mn:CTO	55.50 wt-%	44.07 wt-%	0.42 wt-%
Fe:CTO	55.50 wt-%	44.07 wt-%	0.43 wt-%
Co:CTO	55.49 wt%	44.06 wt-%	0.45 wt-%

Finally, the powders were milled in 2-propanol in the same attrition mill set-up for 2 h at 700 rpm to break up agglomerates formed during calcination. Then the same drying and sieving steps were applied. Subsequently, the powders were investigated regarding phase purity using X-Ray diffraction (XRD) (Philips X'pert – MPD Type 3040/00, Netherlands) ensuring successful solid-state synthesis of the desired compound.

3.2 Sample preparation and microstructure measurements

The prepared powders were used to press pellet shaped green bodies of 8 mm in diameter and around 4 mm in height. The green bodies were first pressed in a uniaxial press (30 MPa) and then further densified by cold isostatic pressing at a maximum pressure of 150 MPa.

To quantify grain growth, for each material and temperature a base value d_0 as starting value for grain growth was determined. Since sintering stages I and II are mostly neck formation and shrinkage and grain growth only dominates stage III of sintering, a sufficient density of around 90 % should be reached before the isothermal sintering. This is the point where the network of open pores is closed and sintering stage III is initiated.[20] For that purpose, the pressed green bodies were first heated up to the desired temperature in air and the furnace was shut down without any dwell time. These samples were then investigated regarding their density using Archimedes principle[21] to confirm closed porosity and the initiation of the third sintering stage. All of the samples showed an initial density ρ_0 of more than 96% after this process.

Grain growth experiments were conducted for all materials between 1350 °C and 1500 °C in air. For microstructure observations the sintered samples were embedded in epoxy resin, ground and polished, starting with 15 µm diamond suspension, followed by 6 µm, 3 µm and 1 µm. Finally, the samples were thermally etched and coated with carbon to reduce charge effects during Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) observations. Microstructure images of each sample were taken using SEM (FEI Helios NanoLab600) and used for determination of mean grain sizes d . Measurements were done

on at least two different micrographs of each sample for at least 300 grains using line intercept method in ImageJ.[22] No correction factor was applied.

For the calculation of the grain growth rate k further samples were sintered in air at varying dwell times t and their mean grain sizes d were identified. The measured grain sizes were fitted to the grain growth law by Burke and Turnbull.[23]

$$d^2 - d_0^2 = k \cdot t \quad (1)$$

To ensure a good fit, at least three samples sintered at the same temperature T and different dwell times t were measured.

3.3 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

Samples for electrochemical impedance measurements were ground to remove the surface layers and to ensure a uniform thickness of around 2 mm. For conductivity, the top and the bottom of the samples were coated with Ag-paste (6120, Koartan, US), which was dried at 150 °C and subsequently fired at 850 °C for 10 min. Measurements were performed with a NEISYS analyzer (Novocontrol, Germany) in a temperature range from 800-400 °C (step-size: 25 °C) and frequencies between $10^7 - 10^{-1}$ Hz in air. Two measurements over the full frequency range at every temperature step were performed. The first measurement was used for equilibration of the sample at the given temperature and discarded, the second measurement was used for analysis. The resulting data were fitted in RelaxIS3 (rhd instruments, Germany) using an equivalent circuit according to the brick-layer model.[24] The brick-layer model equivalent circuit is a series of parallel resistance (R) and constant phase elements (CPE), each representing a different region of the ceramic: bulk, grain boundary and electrode/surface [(R_{bulk}||CPE_{bulk})- (R_{grain-boundary}||CPE_{grain-boundary})- (R_{electrode}||CPE_{electrode})]. Different regions show different relaxation times and can therefore be distinguished. In the present work the materials CTO Cr:CTO and Mn:CTO did not show distinguishable processes in the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) and were fitted using only one R||CPE. In the case of Fe:CTO and Co:CTO, it could be differentiated between (R_{bulk}||CPE_{bulk}) and (R_{grain boundary}||CPE_{grain boundary}).

The respective equivalent circuits were used to calculate conductivities σ according to **equation 2**:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R} \cdot \frac{l}{A} \quad (2)$$

with the sample thickness l and the sample area A .

3.4 Scanning Transmission electron microscopy measurements (STEM)

Cross-sectional TEM lamellae were prepared by focused ion beam (FIB) lift-out from the investigated specimens (CTO, Mn:CTO, Fe:CTO). To minimize surface damage and Ga-implantation effects, the

lamellae were subsequently low-energy ion milled prior to STEM analysis. Grain boundaries were first located in STEM mode and inspected using high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) STEM imaging to select suitable boundary segments for chemical mapping.

Elemental distributions were measured by Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (STEM-EDS) spectrum imaging across selected grain boundaries. To reduce channeling-related artifacts in the resulting segregation profiles, the specimen was oriented slightly off-zone during EDS acquisition when required. EDS datasets were processed by standard workflows including background subtraction, peak deconvolution, and generation of elemental maps. Quantitative line profiles across grain boundaries were extracted from the spectrum images by integrating intensities over a narrow rectangular region oriented normal to the grain-boundary plane. Because absorption and residual channeling effects can influence absolute quantification in thin foils, the EDS results are reported primarily in terms of relative changes (enrichment or depletion) across the boundary rather than absolute site fractions.

3.5 Phase field modelling

The influence of space charge layer induced solute drag effects on the grain growth kinetics was simulated using the defect-chemistry informed phase-field model.[25] An acceptor-doped (A'_{Ti}) $CaTiO_3$ polycrystalline system consisting of n grains was considered. Within this framework, a free-energy-based Kim-Kim-Suzuki (KKS) phase-field model was constructed. A set of non-conserved order parameters η_i ($i=1\dots n$) was introduced to distinguish different grains, while conserved concentration fields $C_{V_{\bar{O}}}$ and C_{dop} were used to describe the concentrations of oxygen vacancies and acceptor dopants, respectively. In addition, an electrostatic field ϕ was incorporated to represent the spatial distribution of the electrostatic potential arising from charged defects. Then the formulation of the total free energy density functional is given by

$$\mathcal{F} = \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{1}{2} \kappa \sum_{i=1}^n |\nabla \eta_i|^2 + \omega \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\eta_i^4}{4} - \frac{\eta_i^2}{2} + \frac{3}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j>i}^n \eta_i^2 \eta_j^2 + \frac{1}{4} \right) + f^{ech} \right] d\Omega, \quad (3)$$

where κ is the coefficient of the gradient term, ω is the free energy barrier coefficient. The parameters κ and ω can be determined via the grain boundary core width (w_c) and the grain boundary energy (σ). In this work, only the influence of solute drag effects is investigated, therefore, isotropic grain boundary properties were chosen in order to remove other complexities. Their relations can be expressed as $\sigma = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \sqrt{\kappa \omega}$ and $w_c = \sqrt{\frac{8\kappa}{\omega}}$. f^{ech} is the electrochemical free energy contribution, which is given by

$$f^{ech} = [1 - h(\eta)] f_b^{ech}(C_{V_{\bar{O},b}}, C_{dop}) + h(\eta) f_c^{ech}(C_{V_{\bar{O},c}}, C_{dop,c}) - \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r}{2} (\nabla \phi)^2, \quad (4)$$

with the subscripts b and c indicating the bulk phase and grain boundary core, respectively. ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity and ϵ_r is the relative permittivity. For CTO, $\epsilon_r = 170$ was assumed.[26] $h(\eta)$ is the interpolation function and is given by

$$h(\eta) = \frac{4}{3} \left[1 - 4 \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i^3 + 3 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i^2 \right)^2 \right]. \quad (5)$$

In addition, $f_b^{\text{ech}}(C_{V_{\ddot{o}}}, C_{\text{dop},b})$ and $f_c^{\text{ech}}(C_{V_{\ddot{o}}}, C_{\text{dop},c})$ denote the electrochemical free energy contributions from the bulk and grain boundary core, respectively, with $C_{V_{\ddot{o}}}$ and $C_{\text{dop},b}$ being the phase concentrations of oxygen vacancy and acceptor dopant in the bulk phase, while $C_{V_{\ddot{o}}}$ and $C_{\text{dop},c}$ being the phase concentrations of oxygen vacancy and dopant in the grain boundary core. Local concentrations ($C_{V_{\ddot{o}}}$ and C_{dop}) are treated as the mixture of phase concentrations in bulk and grain boundary core. The relations between local concentration and phase concentration are expressed as

$$C_{V_{\ddot{o}}} = [1 - h(\eta)]C_{V_{\ddot{o}},b} + h(\eta)C_{V_{\ddot{o}},c} \quad (6)$$

and

$$C_{\text{dop}} = [1 - h(\eta)]C_{\text{dop},b} + h(\eta)C_{\text{dop},c}. \quad (7)$$

In the principle of defect chemistry, the electrochemical free energies $f_b^{\text{ech}}(C_{V\ddot{o},b}, C_{dop,b})$ and $f_c^{\text{ech}}(C_{V\ddot{o},c}, C_{dop,c})$ are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
f_b^{\text{ech}}(C_{V\ddot{o},b}, C_{dop,b}) &= \mu_{V\ddot{o},b}^0 C_{V\ddot{o},b} + \mu_{dop,b}^0 C_{dop,b} \\
&+ k_B T \left[C_{V\ddot{o},b} \ln \left(\frac{C_{V\ddot{o},b}}{N_{V\ddot{o},b}} \right) + (N_{V\ddot{o},b} - C_{V\ddot{o},b}) \ln \left(\frac{N_{V\ddot{o},b} - C_{V\ddot{o},b}}{N_{V\ddot{o},b}} \right) \right. \\
&+ C_{dop,b} \ln \left(\frac{C_{dop,b}}{N_{dop,b}} \right) + (N_{dop,b} - C_{dop,b}) \ln \left(\frac{N_{dop,b} - C_{dop,b}}{N_{dop,b}} \right) \left. \right] \\
&+ (z_{V\ddot{o}} C_{V\ddot{o},b} + z_{dop} C_{dop,b}) e \phi
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
f_c^{\text{ech}}(C_{V\ddot{o},c}, C_{dop,c}) &= \mu_{V\ddot{o},c}^0 C_{V\ddot{o},c} + \mu_{dop,c}^0 C_{dop,c} \\
&+ k_B T \left[C_{V\ddot{o},c} \ln \left(\frac{C_{V\ddot{o},c}}{N_{V\ddot{o},c}} \right) + (N_{V\ddot{o},c} - C_{V\ddot{o},c}) \ln \left(\frac{N_{V\ddot{o},c} - C_{V\ddot{o},c}}{N_{V\ddot{o},c}} \right) \right. \\
&+ C_{dop,c} \ln \left(\frac{C_{dop,c}}{N_{dop,c}} \right) + (N_{dop,c} - C_{dop,c}) \ln \left(\frac{N_{dop,c} - C_{dop,c}}{N_{dop,c}} \right) \left. \right] + (z_{V\ddot{o}} C_{V\ddot{o},c} \\
&+ z_{dop} C_{dop,c}) e \phi
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where $\mu_{V\ddot{o},b}^0$, $\mu_{V\ddot{o},c}^0$, $\mu_{dop,b}^0$ and $\mu_{dop,c}^0$ are standard formation energies of oxygen vacancy and dopant in bulk and grain boundary core. $N_{V\ddot{o},b}$, $N_{dop,b}$, $N_{V\ddot{o},c}$ and $N_{dop,c}$ are numbers of available sites per unit volume for oxygen vacancy and dopant in bulk and grain boundary core. Here, B-site dopant and oxygen vacancy are treated as parts of different sub-lattices in order to correctly represent the respective configurational entropy. In addition, the local structure within the grain boundary core differs from that of the bulk. These structural differences can significantly alter the number of available sites for both dopants and oxygen vacancies. Therefore, it is necessary to treat the number of available sites for oxygen vacancies and dopants in the grain boundary core as distinct from those in the bulk and these quantities play a critical role in determining the SCL. $z_{V\ddot{o}}$ and z_{dop} are valance numbers of oxygen vacancy and dopant. k_B , T and e are Boltzmann constant, temperature and the elementary charge, respectively.

Then, the evolution of phase-field order parameters for grain i with isotropic grain boundary properties follows the Allen-Cahn equation, and is given by

$$\frac{1}{L} \frac{\partial \eta_i}{\partial t} = \nabla \kappa \nabla \eta_i - \omega \left(\eta_i^3 - \eta_i + 3 \sum_{j=1; j \neq i}^n \eta_i \eta_j^2 \right) + h'(\eta) \left[f_b^{ech} - f_c^{ech} - \frac{\partial f_b^{ech}}{\partial C_{V\ddot{o},b}} (C_{V\ddot{o},b} - C_{V\ddot{o},c}) - \frac{\partial f_b^{ech}}{\partial C_{dop,b}} (C_{dop,b} - C_{dop,c}) \right] \quad (10)$$

with L being the grain boundary mobility. The evolution of the conserved concentration fields $C_{V\ddot{o}}$ and C_{dop} are expressed as

$$\frac{\partial C_{V\ddot{o}}}{\partial t} = \nabla \left(M_{V\ddot{o}} \nabla \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{V\ddot{o}}} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_{dop}}{\partial t} = \nabla \left(M_{dop} \nabla \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{dop}} \right) \quad (12)$$

where $M_{V\ddot{o}}$ and M_{dop} are mobilities of oxygen vacancy and dopant, which are given by

$$M_{V\ddot{o}} = D_{V\ddot{o}} / (\partial^2 f^{ech} / \partial C_{V\ddot{o}}^2) \quad (13)$$

and

$$M_{dop} = D_{dop} / (\partial^2 f^{ech} / \partial C_{dop}^2) \quad (14)$$

with $D_{V\ddot{o}}$ and D_{dop} being the diffusivities of oxygen vacancy and dopant, respectively. Moreover, the phase concentration of oxygen vacancy and dopant follows the constrains

$$\frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{V\ddot{o}}} = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{V\ddot{o},b}} = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{V\ddot{o},c}}, \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{dop}} = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{dop,b}} = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta C_{dop,c}}. \quad (16)$$

In addition, the governing equation of electrostatic potential field is obtained by Poisson's equation

$$\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \nabla^2 \phi = z_{V\ddot{o}} e C_{V\ddot{o}} + z_{dop} e C_{dop}. \quad (17)$$

The numerical implementation of the defect-chemistry informed phase-field model is carried out via finite element method (FEM) in Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) framework. The polycrystalline microstructure consisting of 1000 grains is initialized using a Voronoi tessellation method, in which each grain is assigned a unique grain index. The simulation temperature is 1673 K. The grain boundary core width is set to 0.8 nm, consistent with the physical value.[12] The simulation domain is set to 512 nm \times 512 nm, with an initial mesh spacing of $\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.4$ nm. To ensure numerical accuracy, the relative convergence tolerance is set to 10^{-8} . The difference in segregation energy of oxygen vacancy between grain boundary core and bulk is -1.0 eV, while that of acceptor dopant is -0.5 eV. The diffusivity of Fe is set to 1.3×10^{-11} m²/s,[27]. The diffusion coefficients of the specific dopants in CaTiO₃ are unknown but their ratios in comparison with Fe were estimated from the grain growth rates given in **figure 5**. The resulting ratios for diffusivities of Mn, Cr and Co are $D_{Co}/D_{Fe} = 0.01$, $D_{Cr}/D_{Fe} = 0.1$, $D_{Mn}/D_{Fe} = 10$, respectively.

To improve computational efficiency while maintaining numerical accuracy, an adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) strategy is employed. The mesh is dynamically refined in regions with large phase-field gradients, particularly near grain boundaries, while coarser grids are used in grain interior regions where the fields vary slowly. To further optimize memory usage during the simulations, the grain tracker algorithm is employed. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to all edges of the simulation domain for both the phase-field and concentration fields. For the electrostatic potential field, the bottom-left corner is grounded, while the remaining edges are treated with periodic boundary conditions. Each simulation is performed on 8 computing nodes (a total of 768 CPU cores) with 3072 GB of memory and requires approximately 30 days to complete.

4 Results

4.1 Phase analysis

The prepared powders were investigated regarding their phase purity using XRD. The resulting diffractograms after calcination for 4h at 915°C are shown in **figure 2**. For all the materials the orthorhombic perovskite phase (Pbnm) was present. Reflexes of the Pbnm phase were not highlighted. The highlighted reflexes belong to educt phases. A slight remaining amount of Rutile (TiO₂) was also present in all the powders, which can be identified by the peak at 27.46°[28]. This is due to a slight excess in TiO₂ when mixing the powders, to avoid the formation of Ca-rich secondary phases, during the solid-state reaction of TiO₂ and CaCO₃ to CaTiO₃ and CO₂. In the case of Co:CTO the CaO reflex at $2\theta = 32.3^\circ$ shows, indicating no full conversion during solid state synthesis.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of calcined powders. All reflexes that are not highlighted belong to the desired Pbnm phase. Reflexes of educt and intermediate phases are indicated by dotted lines. (The reflex at 32.3° only visible in Co:CTO can also be associated to CaO.)

4.2 Microstructure analysis and grain growth

To determine the microstructure evolution of the differently doped materials with sintering parameters a detailed SEM study was done. One example of such a microstructure evolution experiment for the lowest sintering temperature of 1350°C is shown in **figure 3**. This temperature was chosen as representative, since the differences in microstructure development between the observed materials are most significant.

At the initial stage (0 h) all materials showed remaining porosity, independent of the sintering temperature. The initial densities are shown in table S1 (supplementary information). The densities of higher than 90% and the low area fraction of pores in the micrographs indicate that the final stage of the sintering process was reached. No open porosity was present and the dominating process during this stage of sintering was grain growth, rather than further densification.

In some cases, slight pore coarsening was visible during annealing, i.e. for undoped CTO and Fe:CTO (**figures 3 a), b), c), and j), k), l)**), at lower and higher sintering temperatures. Cr:CTO showed a distinct coarsening of pores at higher sintering temperatures. In Mn:CTO, pore coarsening was not observed. However, the pores were redistributed over sintering time: At the initial stage the pores are predominantly located at grain boundaries and/ or triple points. During isothermal sintering, pore separation occurred and their position changes from the grain boundaries to the centers of the grains. This phenomenon is more pronounced at higher sintering temperatures. Besides redistribution and coarsening of pores, significant grain growth can be observed at 1350°C. The increase in grain size over time is highest for the undoped CaTiO₃ at an early stage (between 0-1h).

At all temperatures, the increase in grain size is significantly more pronounced for undoped CaTiO₃ compared to the acceptor-doped materials. The average grain sizes for the samples sintered at 1350°C in air are shown in **figure 4**. The undoped sample shows fast grain growth and reaches a plateau rather quickly, after around 3 h. This material also shows largest final grain size of around 7.2 μm. It is worth mentioning that Mn:CTO shows the smallest final grain size, but also smallest initial grain size d_0 . However, over the sintering time of 10 hours coarsening is evident and the development of grain size over time is similar to that of Fe:CTO.

The development of grain sizes with heating times for all investigated temperatures is depicted in **figure S1**. While grain growth is faster at higher temperatures, the overall trend is similar: undoped CaTiO₃ has largest grain sizes and exhibits fastest grain growth. Also, the development of grain size over heating time of Co:CTO and Cr:CTO is very similar.

Figure 3: Microstructures of samples sintered at 1350°C. Microstructures of samples without isothermal sintering (a, d, g, j, m) show highest remaining porosity. Samples sintered isothermally for 10h (c, f, i, l, o) have distinctly coarser microstructures. In case of CTO (c) and Fe:CTO (l) pore coarsening can be observed.

Figure 4: Grain size development over annealing time for different CaTiO_3 materials at 1350°C. For CTO the grain size increases strongly in the initial stage (up to three hours) before the grain growth slows down. This behavior is similar but less distinct for the acceptor-doped materials (Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO, Fe:CTO, Co:CTO).

The grain growth rates, calculated for the different materials from the experimental data using the model developed by Burke and Turnbull (**equation 1**) are given in the Arrhenius plot in **figure 5**.

For all temperatures, undoped CTO shows highest grain growth rates, at low sintering temperatures up to an order of magnitude higher than the Cr:CTO and Co:CTO. The Arrhenius fits (lines in **figure 5**) indicate the increase of grain growth constants with higher temperatures for all materials. Mn:CTO has grain growth rates higher than the other acceptor doped materials for all temperatures, but 1350 °C. At 1500°C, k of Mn:CTO matches the value of undoped CTO, which is unexpected compared to all lower temperatures. The highest and the lowest sintering temperature were excluded for the fit function in this case, since they deviate strongly from Arrhenius-type behavior of the other datapoints. Cr:CTO and Co:CTO show smallest grain growth at lower sintering temperatures. As the heating temperatures are increased, the grain growth coefficients of Cr:CTO, Fe:CTO, and Co:CTO become more similar.

Figure 5: Grain growth rates of the respective materials vs. temperature and corresponding Arrhenius fits. Open symbols are grain growth coefficients calculated from phase field models. Doped materials show less grain growth except for Mn:CTO at 1500°C, where the grain growth rate is similar to the one found for CTO. In all cases the increase of grain growth with sintering temperature (activation energy) is quite low.

A grain growth transition, often visible by a distinct step in the Arrhenius plot as reported mainly for STO, but also other perovskites [17,29] is absent in this temperature range in CaTiO₃ materials. However, Fe-doped and undoped CaTiO₃ show a similar trend in grain growth constants over temperature, with a rather small total increase in grain growth over the range of 150°C. Moreover, between 1350°C and 1425°C, k is almost constant, with a slight decrease in grain growth between 1350°C and 1400°C. In the case of Cr:CTO and Co:CTO, some of the data points deviate strongly from

the fit function. Especially in case of Cr:CTO, the scattering of the grain growth coefficient is rather high.

Mn:CTO shows a similar trend as Fe:CTO for most temperatures, just for the lowest and the highest sintering temperatures the grain growth rate deviates distinctly. At 1500°C the grain growth is similar to undoped CaTiO₃, at 1350°C it is by an order of magnitude lower.

4.3 Grain boundary properties

Grain-boundary chemistry in CaTiO₃ was assessed by STEM-EDS spectrum imaging to directly verify dopant redistribution and its relation to grain growth behavior. High-Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) images of grain boundaries in CTO, Fe:CTO and Mn:CTO are shown in **figures 6 a), e) and h)**, respectively. In undoped CTO (**figure 6 a-d)**), Ca, Ti, and O maps show a weak but detectable compositional gradient in the vicinity of the boundary.

In contrast, Fe:CTO exhibits distinct Fe segregation at the grain boundary (**fig. 6 f)**). The Fe map shows clear enrichment localized to the boundary core, and the extracted line profile (**figure 6 g)**) displays a sharp segregation peak centered at the interface. In addition, the boundary-centered Fe peak is accompanied by correlated variations in Ca, Ti, and O across the same region.

On the other hand, Mn:CTO shows no evidence of Mn segregation (**figure 6 i, j)**). Neither the Mn map nor the concentration profile reveals a boundary-centered enrichment feature.

Figure 6: Microstructures and element mappings of CTO (a -d), Fe:CTO (e, f) and Mn:CTO (h, i). g) and j) show quantified concentration line profile extracted normal to the boundary plane of Fe-doped and Mn-doped CaTiO_3 , respectively

The grain boundary properties were furthermore investigated by impedance spectroscopy. **Figures 7 a** and **b** show the result of the measurements at 800°C in a Nyquist plot. The spectra representing Cr:CTO and Mn:CTO show highest resistivity at this temperature, followed by undoped CTO. The resistivity of Fe:CTO is lower, and in this case a distinct second arc (representing the grain boundary contribution) is present. This is similar for Co:CTO; here, the resistivity is significantly lower than for the other materials at this temperature. The conductivities over a temperature range of $800\text{-}600^\circ\text{C}$ are depicted in **figure 7c**. For CTO, Cr:CTO and Mn:CTO only total conductivities were calculated, as the spectra that did not allow a differentiation between the respective processes. The activation energies of conductivity, represented by the slope of all the acceptor-doped materials (except Co:CTO) are quite similar, around $E_A(\text{Cr:CTO/Mn:CTO/Fe:CTO}) = 1.5 \text{ eV}$. Undoped CTO has a slightly higher activation energy for conduction ($E_A(\text{CTO})=1.75 \text{ eV}$) and Co:CTO the lowest ($E_A(\text{Co:CTO})=1.10 \text{ eV}$). The grain boundary conductivities of Fe:CTO and Co:CTO are higher than the bulk conductivities, but the activation energies in case of Co:CTO differ by a factor of around two ($E_A^{\text{gb}}(\text{Co:CTO})=1.83 \text{ eV}$ and $E_A^{\text{b}}(\text{Co:CTO})=0.93 \text{ eV}$).

Figure 7: a) Nyquist plot of impedance of CTO materials, b) shows a magnification of the Nyquist plot of Co:CTO, c) shows the conductivity of the different materials calculated from the impedance measurements

4.4 Grain growth model

The phase-field simulation results are presented in **figure 8**, including the grain microstructure (**a**), **e**), **i**), **m**), the distribution of acceptor dopant concentration c_{dop} (**b**), **f**), **j**), **n**), the oxygen vacancy concentration c_{V_O} (**c**), **g**), **k**), **o**), and the electrostatic potential Φ (**d**), **h**), **l**), **p**) at 1400 °C for a sintering time of one hour.

The microstructure evolution is rather similar for Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO and Fe:CTO. Just Co:CTO shows distinctly smaller grain size after one hour of sintering. The grain size development is fitted by using the relation given in **equation 1**: $d^2 - d_0^2 = kt$. The average area of grains at different simulation times was obtained and used to calculate the grain growth rate k from the grain growth simulations. The simulations yield the dimensionless parameter k for Co:CTO, Cr:CTO, Fe:CTO and Mn:CTO are 0.40, 0.80, 0.91 and 0.99, corresponding to 1.78×10^{-15} m²/s, 3.56×10^{-15} m²/s, 4.13×10^{-15} m²/s and 4.41×10^{-15} m²/s at 1400 °C, respectively.

The dopant and oxygen vacancy redistribution to the grain boundaries is strongest in Mn:CTO (**fig. 8 f** & **g**)), where there are strong differences in dopant concentrations between grain boundary and bulk (i.e. segregation and depletion) visible. There are no areas of higher dopant concentrations visible inside the grains, whereas for the other materials, especially Cr:CTO (**fig. 8 b**) and Fe:CTO (**fig. 8 k**) there are areas of elevated dopant concentration inside the grains, that resemble former grain boundaries. Co:CTO shows accumulation of oxygen vacancies at the grain boundary core (**fig. 8 o**)), but a strong segregation of acceptor species toward the grain boundary is not visible after one hour of sintering time (**fig. 8 n**)). This redistribution has direct influence on the grain boundary potential Φ (**fig.**

8 d), h), l), p)). The potential is highest in the case of Co:CTO, followed by Mn:CTO. Fe:CTO has lowest grain boundary potential after the heat treatment.

Figure 8: Phase field simulations of acceptor doped CaTiO_3 : microstructure, dopant concentration (C_{dop}), oxygen vacancy concentration (C_{V_O}) and electrostatic potential (Φ) after sintering in air at 1400°C for one hour. Mn:CTO shows strongest differences in dopant concentration between grain boundary and bulk (f). Redistribution and oxygen vacancies influence the grain boundary potential which is highest in Co:CTO (p) and lowest in Fe:CTO (l).

5 Discussion

In the present work, CaTiO₃ materials were synthesized and investigated regarding their grain growth behavior and grain boundary properties. Solid state synthesis led to formation of the orthorhombic perovskite phase. Small amounts of Titania that were still detectable in the powders by XRD after calcination were not observable in the microstructures by SEM. Accordingly, full conversion of the remaining educts to the perovskite phase probably only happens at elevated temperatures.

The grain growth rates for all the investigated compositions vary slightly. Overall, there is a trend of faster grain growth at higher temperatures. A distinct grain boundary transition as reported by Rheinheimer *et.al.* for SrTiO₃ [18] could not be observed. However, the slower grain growth of the doped materials indicate solute drag occurs, and the shallow slope and the comparably small differences in grain growth rates along with the mostly unimodal microstructures imply that the difference between dragged and non-dragged grain boundaries in CaTiO₃ is small compared to SrTiO₃.

The results in this work allow two explanations for the difference in grain growth rates for the different materials: Since the dopant concentrations in all acceptor doped materials are similar, the effect on solute drag depends on the respective dopant species and its diffusivity. Diffusion coefficients for the respective species in CaTiO₃ are not known, but depend on diffusion mechanism, size mismatch between the host lattice ions and the diffusing species, as well as charge mismatch [30]. For the assumption that all the acceptor dopants are present in a 3+ valence state, therefor showing a similar driving force for accumulation at the grain boundary, their diffusivity during grain growth should be mainly depending on their ionic radius. Table 2 summarizes the ionic radii of the dopant species:

Table 2: ionic radii of the different dopants, assuming a 6-fold coordination and 3+-valence state[31]

Species	Ionic radius	
Ti ⁴⁺	0.605 Å	
Cr ³⁺	0.615 Å	
Mn ³⁺	0.58 Å (low spin)	0.645 Å (high spin)
Fe ³⁺	0.55 Å (low spin)	0.645 Å (high spin)
Co ³⁺	0.545 Å (low spin)	0.61 Å (high spin)

The B-site in oxide perovskites exhibits octahedral splitting (TiO₆), the early 3d ions like Mn³⁺ (d⁴) and Fe³⁺(d⁵) are generally expected to have high spin configuration, whereas Co³⁺(d⁶) could be present either in low spin or high spin.[32–34]

Considering Co:CTO shows the lowest grain growth across nearly all investigated temperatures, this behavior likely relates to the similarity between the ionic radii of Co³⁺ and Ti⁴⁺. When the size mismatch

between the dopant and host cation is minimal, diffusion within the lattice is facilitated. As a result, point defects can more readily migrate along grain boundaries and interact with them more effectively, thereby reducing grain boundary mobility and, consequently, suppressing grain growth[14]. Therefore, Co^{3+} is assumed to be present in its high spin configuration as a dopant in CaTiO_3 and has ionic radius of 0.61 Å in a six-fold coordination, exhibiting the smallest size mismatch. This assumption is still to be confirmed. The mismatch between Ti^{4+} and Cr^{3+} is slightly larger, making it harder for dopant species to follow grain boundary movement and reducing interaction, which results in a similar trend but slightly less solute drag for Cr:CTO. Following this argumentation, Fe:CTO should show less solute drag which holds true for low sintering temperatures.

Overall, the values for grain growth constants found experimentally differ from the calculated ones. Since the diffusion coefficients for the respective dopants were only roughly estimated, this is not surprising. The overall trend, however, is in good agreement with what could be found experimentally: Co:CTO shows least grain growth and the constants of Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO and Fe:CTO differ only slightly from one another, which corresponds to the Arrhenius fits in **figure 6** at moderate temperatures. The defect concentration distributions simulated in the phase field model given in **figure 8 b), f), j), n)** could not be confirmed experimentally. STEM-EDS images of Mn:CTO and Fe:CTO are almost contrary to the simulation results; Fe segregates strongly toward the grain boundary, while there could be no Mn enrichment found in the vicinity of the grain boundary in Mn:CTO. Especially for high grain boundary potentials and a highly different chemistry of grain boundary and bulk a distinct arc representing the grain boundary contribution to the impedance would be expected to be visible in the respective Nyquist-plot (**figures 7 a & b**). This only holds true for Co:CTO, where the grain boundary potential is highest and a strong accumulation of oxygen vacancies is present in the simulation. Fe:CTO, which showed a distinct grain boundary contribution in the impedance measurements does not exhibit a large difference in potential between grain boundary and bulk, nor strong accumulation or segregation compared to Mn:CTO or Co:CTO. This shows, that the diffusion coefficients alone are not sufficient to explain the difference in microstructure evolution and grain boundary properties in doped CaTiO_3 .

Another explanation for the difference in grain growth behavior is the charge state of the respective dopant. The reason for the rather high grain growth constant of Mn:CTO lies in the amphoteric nature of Manganese: Findings of studies of Mn-doped SrTiO_3 show that Manganese is present as Mn_{Ti}^x as well as Mn_{Sr}^x depending on A/B ratio and oxygen partial pressure.[35–37] Experimental evidence from EPR and X-ray absorption spectroscopy, supported by first-principles calculations, indicates that Manganese in CaTiO_3 preferentially substitutes on the Ca-site as Mn^{2+} rather than on the Ti-site as $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ [3]. Since the A/B ratio was chosen to be 0.995 to avoid Ca-rich secondary phases, chances are, that Mn is mainly present as Mn^{2+} As STEM/EDS images revealed, this strongly affects the segregation behavior, since there is lesser/no electrostatic driving force that stabilizes Manganese

species at the grain boundary. Hence, solute drag is significantly lower for Mn:CTO compared to Fe:CTO or Co:CTO species. The fact, that conductivities are similar to CTO (**figure 7 c**)) supports the theory, that doping of CaTiO_3 with Manganese does not result in a significant increase in the concentration of charged defects.

At 1350°C, the lowest sintering temperature, Mn:CTO has a rather low grain growth constant, about an order of magnitude smaller than undoped CaTiO_3 . At this temperature the dragging force is significantly higher than at high temperatures, suggesting a higher fraction of Mn'_{Ti} . Furthermore, the conductivity at lower sintering temperatures is higher than that of undoped CTO, also indicating a higher fraction of charged defects. However, there are no reports about the temperature dependence of preferred substitution site of Mn in perovskite oxides and further investigations have to be conducted to support this theory.

The schematic drawing in **figure 9** shows the assumed charge transition levels of the different dopant species in CaTiO_3 . The green line indicates roughly the assumed position of the Fermi level in this model. This schematic is mostly based on findings for BaTiO_3 , which is much better investigated and understood.[7] Similar to BaTiO_3 , the $\text{Co}^{3+/2+}$ transition is assumed to occur at low energies. Co_{Ti}'' has higher driving force to segregate to the grain boundary and lead to higher defect concentration in the system through compensation mechanisms. This is in good agreement with the findings of this work: Co:CTO shows most solute drag and highest bulk conductivity caused by a high defect concentration due to compensation mechanisms. The $3+/2+$ transition of Fe is at higher energies, leading to Fe_{Ti}' , which has lower driving force for segregation, but still segregates to the grain boundaries, causing solute drag. This aligns well with the faster grain growth in comparison to Co:CTO. Also, the conductivity indicates a different defect chemistry with overall lower defect concentration in Fe:CTO. A tendency to segregate is visible in STEM images, which is absent in Mn:CTO. Since the conductivities of Mn:CTO and Cr:CTO are almost equivalent, the defect chemistry of these materials is likely very similar. The $\text{Cr}^{4+/3+}$ level is at high energies within the band gap, making it a neutral defect. Hence, the concentration of compensating defects (like $\text{V}_{\text{O}}^{\bullet\bullet}$) that contribute to conductivity is similar to undoped CaTiO_3 . However, the charge transport mechanisms are likely similar in Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO and Fe:CTO, since they have a very similar activation energy of conductivity. The difference in activation energies between Co:CTO and the other materials suggest a different compensation mechanism. Following this argumentation, the reason for the difference in grain growth could be due to the tendency of Mn to occupy the Ca- and the Ti-site, which changes the A/B-ratio. In many perovskite systems, this has shown to have a strong influence on microstructure [38–41] but only little influence on conductivity[42,43].

Figure 9: Assumed charge transition levels of transition metal dopants on Ti-site in CaTiO_3 adopted from ref. [7] The green line indicates the approximate position of the Fermi level E_F . Yellow dots represent the positions of the 4+/3+ transition level, blue dots the 3+/2+ transitions of the respective transition metal.

6 Conclusion

In this study, acceptor-doped CaTiO_3 materials were synthesized using solid state synthesis. Phase-pure powders were obtained and used for further investigation. Microstructure evolution was evaluated by heat treatments and SEM observation. Specific grain boundaries were investigated by STEM-EDS, and impedance measurements were conducted to analyze the electrochemical response of the ceramic samples. Different diffusion coefficients were estimated to simulate grain growth in a phase field model.

CaTiO_3 shows a dopant-specific segregation behavior. A grain boundary transition, like reported on in literature for other perovskite oxides was not observable in the investigated temperature region. The shallow slopes and small differences in grain growth constants between differently doped materials indicate, however, that solute drag is the cause for different grain growth rates, but the difference in mobility of dragged and non-dragged grain boundaries is quite small. The phase field model yielded results that were consistent with the grain growth rates that were found experimentally and allows and explanation for the different grain growth rates which is strictly based on diffusion coefficients of A'_{Ti} . The absence of segregation of Mn to the grain boundary visible in STEM/EDS images and corresponding line scans and different conductivities indicate that diffusion coefficients are not solely the determining factors in segregation behavior and solute drag in CaTiO_3 . The different charge transition levels of the respective dopant species cause them to be present at different valence states in the lattice. This strongly influences the driving force of segregation and the stabilization behavior of charged defects in vicinity of the grain boundary. The respective charge states of the dopants are to be determined by XPS or EPR to validate this hypothesis.

7 Acknowledgement

The FIB-SEM Thermo Fisher Helios NanoLab 600 used in this study was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) (No. 154585072). The authors thank the DFG for funding within the collaborative research center 1548 FLAIR (No. 463184206), subprojects B03, B04 and B06. WR thanks the DFG for funding within the ENP RH 146/1-1 (No. 435025113).

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8 Supplementary

Density of the initial samples: (t=0h)

	1350°C	1375°C	1400°C	1425°C	1450°C	1475°C	1500°C
CTO	96.7%	97.3%	97.5%	97.9%	97.1%	97.2%	97.8%
Cr:CTO	98.4%	98.4%	98.5%	97.8%	98.0%	97.9%	98.1%
Mn:CTO	90.6%	90.1%	90.7%	93.3%	93.8%	94.2%	93.7%
Fe:CTO	98.6%	97.9%	98.2%	97.5%	98.1%	97.7%	98.1%
Co:CTO	96.5%	97.3%	98.0%	98.3%	98.4%	98.4%	98.5%

Figure S 1: Development of grain sizes over sintering time for CTO, Cr:CTO, Mn:CTO, Fe:CTO and Co:CTO. For all temperatures, CTO largest grain sizes.